

PHILOSOPHICAL SCIENCES

PHILOSOPHY AS A SCIENCE OF HUMAN DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract

A look at philosophy as a science of human development makes it possible to understand the need to study philosophy in the modern world. According to the author, the reduction of hours devoted to the study of philosophy in Russian universities is the result of a lack of understanding of the difference between knowledge and information, and their role in human life.

In identifying the tasks of human improvement, the author refers to the works of ancient Greek thinkers and religious figures. The difference between natural and acquired human properties noted in the article poses the task of finding ways to harmonize them, which is solved differently in religion and philosophy.

Keywords: philosophy, wisdom, knowledge, information, thinking, reflection, natural human properties, acquired human properties, soul, spirit, harmony, human independence, human education.

Philosophy is one of the oldest sciences, the meaning of which is to improve a person's life. The love of wisdom is generated by a person's desire to answer the key questions of his life: how does the world work? what are the sources of human strength? what should a person do to live with dignity and be useful to people? And to answer these questions, a person must know himself, his properties and abilities, as well as the outside world, natural and created by humans. A person, unlike an animal, can know the meaning and sense of his life. And this knowledge serves as an incentive to improve his life.

Obviously, the topic of this article has both theoretical and practical significance. It was the change in attitudes towards the knowledge of wisdom at the turn of the XX–XXI centuries in the Russian education system that prompted us to turn to the analysis of the significance of what happened. If in the Soviet Union philosophy was studied for two semesters for 110 hours, then in modern Russia university students study philosophy for one semester, and in terms of time – it is two to three times less than earlier. The situation that has arisen is reminiscent of the situation in the middle of the 19th century, when the Minister of Public Education, P.A. Shirinsky-Shikhmatov, "having visited universities, announced that 'the benefits of philosophy have not been proven, but harm from it is possible'" [1, p. 252]. And "in 1850, Nicholas I ordered to abolish teaching of philosophy by secular professors. Departments of history of Philosophy and metaphysics were closed. Philosophy was limited to teaching logic and psychology and transferred to Orthodox priests – professors of theology" [1, p. 252]. The attitude towards philosophy at universities in China or the USA, as well as in European countries, is still respectful. It is enough to watch and listen to recordings of lectures on ethics by Harvard Professor Michael Sandel to be convinced of what has been said.

What is the reason for the changes in modern Russia? It is unlikely that the reduction in the number of hours devoted to the study of philosophy occurred for

political reasons: the current political situation in Russia differs from the situation in the middle of the 19th century. Most likely, modern educational leaders do not attach due importance to the development of a student's thinking in the process of acquiring knowledge, relying on the availability of information. The substitution of knowledge with information does not help to increase the level of conscious independence of the student, which is a key task of education.

What remains behind the "training ship"? There is no single answer to this question, since there is a specific teacher at the helm of the ship, directing it to his favorite places. But we can talk about the possibilities of his choice, referring to the history of the development of human cognition, and not only philosophical, but also mythological, religious, and scientific. Let's talk about these possibilities now. And let's start with the question of the nature of human cognition, what is it like?

The answer to this question is determined by the natural properties and abilities of a person. We know three natural properties of a person: dependence on the external and internal world of his life, uncertainty of his orientation in the world and the rhythmic processes of his body's life. The rhythmicity of life indicates a person's dependence on natural rhythms, but this is a special, dynamic dependence, different in the way of its existence, for example, from gravitational dependence. The rhythm of life served as one of the reasons for the emergence of not only poetry and music, but also various sciences about heaven, earth, and human health.

The property of uncertainty served as the basis of human cognition. At the same time, the feeling of uncertainty experienced by a person is perceived by him as a kind of dependence. Dependence turns out to be a universal characteristic of the existence of all living things on earth. But all living things strive to reduce the degree of their dependence, in other words, they strive for freedom. So, dependence is primary, freedom is secondary. And nature has endowed living beings with the

ability to reduce their dependence by converting the energy of the outside world into their inner world. Natural philosophers considered fire, water, air, and earth as the origin of life, as sources of energy. And the ability of the products of the earth to give strength to man was known much earlier, it was mentioned in the book of Genesis by Moses.

The problem turned out to be the question of the impossibility of expressing in words the unity of movement and rest, presented by Zeno in the aporias "Achilles and the Turtle", "Ehe flying arrow" and others. And only in the 17th century, independently of each other, Newton and Leibniz were able to represent this unity by creating differential calculus.

The discovery of the problems of cognition became the basis for the emergence of the modern meaning of the concept of wisdom. Until that time, those who knew a lot were considered sages. Socrates, as is known, was recognized as one of the first Greek thinkers to be a sage. He openly declared knowledge of his ignorance, speaking at the Athenian court: "I knew about myself that I simply did not know anything..." [2, p. 75].

Knowing about one's ignorance is not the only problem realized by ancient Greek philosophers. A person should be able to determine the measure in various types of activities and relationships: to parents, to elders, to fellow citizens, to enemies, to himself, etc. And education should reveal to a person the meaning of knowledge of measure. This was taught in ancient times. This is indicated by the "Sayings of the Seven Wise Men" from the collection of Demetrius of Phalerum on wisdom.

"1. Cleobulus: Measure is best. 2. Solon: Nothing too much. 4. Thales: Keep up the measure. 5. Pittacus: Know the measure" [3, pp. 92-93].

There is a measure where a person has a choice of actions, which is determined by the existing value system. The teaching of values in ancient times was given serious attention. So Biant, one of the seven ancient Greek sages, advised: "Acquire: in youth – prosperity, in old age – wisdom... You will acquire: by deed – memory [of yourself], by proper measure – caution, by character – nobility, by labor – patience, by fear – piety, by wealth – friendship, by word – conviction, by silence – decorum, by decision – justice, by daring – courage, by deed - power, by glory - supremacy" [3, p. 93]. Today we do not agree with Biant in everything, but the importance of his advice is obvious, and it guides a person to acquire and develop his acquired properties as a person grows up, the content of his activities and the nature of social relations change. Biant's advice is, in fact, advice for improving a person. Most of the advice of other ancient Greek sages is aimed precisely at the formation and development of the properties necessary for human life in society.

Religious teachings have solved and are solving the same problem. One can only wonder at the achieved

level of methodological culture of the authors of the books of the Old and New Testaments. First, they distinguish between the external and internal worlds of human life. So, in the Gospel of Luke, Jesus, when asked by the Pharisees "when the Kingdom of God will come," answered them, "The kingdom of God will not come in a visible way, and they will not say, "Behold, it is here," or, "Behold, it is there." For, behold, the kingdom of God is within you" (Luke 17:20:21).

The content of religious teachings is often aimed at shaping human qualities that promote human unity and peace on earth. In the Sermon on the Mount, Jesus says: "Blessed are the peacemakers, for they will be called the sons of God. Blessed are those who have been exiled for the sake of righteousness, for theirs is the Kingdom of heaven. Blessed are you when they revile you and persecute you and slander me in every way unrighteously (Matthew 5:9:11).

In our opinion, religious education, in comparison with secular education, pays more attention to the formation of mental and spiritual qualities of a person. True, their understanding of the nature of the soul and spirit is different, but not absolutely. In our understanding, the soul is a product of the harmony of feelings, and the spirit is a person's aspiration to achieve ideals. The religious understanding of the soul is similar to Plato's understanding of it. But in both cases, we are talking about human-acquired properties. Of course, the possibility of acquiring them is inherent in the human body.

How natural and acquired human properties combine in our time, in the information age, remains to be explored. The most common way to harmonize them is to play. But work also harmonizes various human properties. However, the methods of teaching creative work have not yet been developed. Let's summarize what we have said.

Philosophy, as the science of human perfection, proceeds from the distinction between natural and acquired properties. Play and work are ways to harmonize them. Religion solves the same problem, but in its own ways. Learning about the differences between secular and religious education enriches both of them and contributes to the effectiveness of human education.

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